
Master's Thesis

Integration of Hydrological Simulations into the Design Process to Assess the Performance of Green Infrastructure Designs

A Case Study of LaPlace, LA

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The Problem

CPRA estimates that flood depths will increase by 30% in 50 years causing a loss of \$24 billion annually

LaPlace after Hurricane Ida, 2021

The 2016 floods in the Baton Rouge and Dehnam Springs area produced a damage toll of at least \$10.1 billion and 13 human casualties. A 1000 year storm.

“Rainfall totals across the region exceeded amounts that would be expected to occur once every 1,000 years (or a less than 0.1% annual probability of occurrence), causing the Amite and Comite Rivers to surge past their banks and resulting in some 50,000 homes across the region filling with more than 18 inches of water” (USGCRP, 2018)

Transitioning to Green Infrastructure

Designed to catch water where it falls with multiple benefits

Improve water quality. Habitat preservation. Biodiversity. Mental health. Economic revitalization. Community gathering. Recreation. Sense of place.

Components of green infrastructure link together to form a functional network

A Green Infrastructure Network

Riparian Edge

Forested Park

Rain garden

Green roof

Bioswale

Simulation as a design tool for quantifying performance of GI

Helping the transition through assessing the performance before construction is CRITICAL for decision making in communities

“Kansas City, MO designed its \$10 million 100-acre Middle Blue River pilot on SWMM predictions and, based on the performance of this 100-acre pilot, it will design its \$2 billion, 20-year consent decree sewer upgrade ”(Matthew Hopton, Ph.D. et al., 2015)

CHALLENGE

Targeted to engineers and
scientist
Lack of software compatibility

SOLUTION

Integration of simulations within
GIS and 3D modeling softwares
allows designers to quantify and
optimize designs from the early
stages

Thesis

Hydrological simulations can be used as a design tool for designers to analyze the feasibility of green infrastructure designs for flash flooding mitigation

The results of this study will provide a framework that can be **replicated for any location in the world**, helping communities transition more easily to green infrastructure strategies and **improving their resilience to climate change.**

**Methodology
Framework**

**Workflow
GRASS GIS
and Grass-
hopper**

**Simulations
r.sim.water**

**Grading in
Docofossor**

Literature Review

Methodology Framework by Urech et al (2022)

Fig. 2. Overview of the methodological approach linking iterative point cloud modeling (a), static (b) and dynamic (c) evaluations, and change detection (d) in a loop.

Urech, P. R. W., Mughal, M. O., & Bartesaghi-Koc, C. (2022). A simulation-based design framework to iteratively analyze and shape urban landscapes using point cloud modeling. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 91, 101731. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2021.101731>

Simulations as tools
for design decision
making

Digital Model

Static representation of the terrain, building, or object

Geospatial Data - Digital Elevation Models and Digital Surface Models
LIDAR - Point clouds
Remote Sensing - Imagery

Digital Twin

'Digital Twin' - combination of the static representation with the continuous change of conditions over time.

Predict how designs will perform when they are implemented

Docofossor

- Cut and fill operations
- Bridge between raster and NURBS
- “Focuses on parametric transformations of a digital terrain model by point, path, area or surface on a digital terrain model (DTM). The collection of computational modeling components operate on a regular grid in 2.5D using distance functions” (Hurkxkens et al, 2019, Docofossor)

Hurkxkens, I., & Bernhard, M. (2019). Computational Terrain Modeling with Distance Functions for Large Scale Landscape Design.

Wichmann Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.14627/537663024>

r.sim.water

- SIMulated Water Erosion Model SIWME: simulat(e) the overland flow phenomenon that directly contributes to flooding.
- Analyzes spatial distribution of shallow overland flow and depth. Does not include riverine waterways. Simulate geophysical properties
- Input data: DEM, water flow gradients, Mannings roughness, diffusion, rainfall excess rate.
- Outputs: raster maps that represent constant water depth and discharge.

Jaroslav Hofierka* and Monika Knutová Simulating spatial aspects of a flash

flood using the Monte Carlo method and GRASS GIS: a case study of the Malá

Svinka Basin (Slovakia)

Methods

1

Defining the Framework

Methods

Define Study Area

LaPlace, Louisiana

Severely affected by flooding

2

Flood Hazard Map

The graphics on this page were done by the author Clara Jimenez during the 2023 Internship at the LSU Coastal Ecosystem Design Studio and served as design inspiration for the case study of this thesis

Proposed Design Inspiration

SLOW, STORE, AND CONNECT

- Blue ways focuses on slowing run off through the naturalization of canals to minimize flood risk.
- The park focuses on stormwater storage.
- All the GI system — community connectivity

Methods

3

Simulation on GRASS GIS — Existing conditions

3

Shallow Water Simulation with r.sim.water Flowchart

Legend

4 Grading with Docofossor Rhino 3D Grasshopper

Grading with Docofossor Flowchart

Results

Context Map

Land Cover

Design Interventions

DEM

Existing Elevation

Proposed Elevation

Results

Water Depth m- 150 mm/hr big storm

EXISTING

PROPOSED

Results

Discharge m³/s- 150 mm/hr big storm

EXISTING

PROPOSED

Results

Analysis with r.univar

The green infrastructure design of a blueway **successfully slows down water** during the storm peak minimizing drainage overflow and flood hazards

Water Depth

At the intervention site, the water storage capacity has been increased by 25%

Added 3,099 m³ of water holding capacity

On the whole study area 0.27% of water storage has been created

Discharge

10 min

On average, 4.7% slower

Maximum speed was reduced by 43%

20 min

On average, 13% slower

Maximum speed reduced by 42%

30 min

Average, 5% slower

Maximum speed reduced by 75%

Existing depth 30 min

Proposed depth 30 min

Existing discharge 30 min

Proposed discharge 30 min

Conclusions

The graphic below was done by the author Clara Jimenez during the 2023 Internship at the LSU Coastal Ecosystem Design Studio and served as design inspiration for the case study of this thesis

Hydrological simulations can be used as a design tool for designers to analyze the feasibility of green infrastructure designs for flash flooding mitigation

The green infrastructure design of a blueway successfully slows down water during the storm peak minimizing drainage overflow and flood hazards

Can be replicated for any location in the world

User friendly, visual, and more efficient data management

Accessible with open source software GRASS GIS

Makes communities transition more easily to GI improving their resilience

Plugins such as Docofossor can be a bridge between GIS and 3D modeling softwares

Future studies on how to integrate computational design across disciplines can facilitate the implementation of green infrastructure technology

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Thank you!